

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Hashimura Juhasz**FIRST NAME:** Alexandra**PROGRAM CODE:** MDIA**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** RP1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 2)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 4–6)
3. American and British English (EUCLID 2019, 24, 27–25)
4. Passive voice (EUCLID 2019, 17, 25)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2019, 24–26, 44)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) (EUCLID 2019, 44–55)
7. Latin expressions and abbreviation (EUCLID 2019, 56–61)

THE JOURNEY BEGINS WITH ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I started my long journey at EUCLID with ACA-401, the International Academic and Professional Paper Writing course. A Japanese proverb says, “A journey of a thousand miles begins with a single step.” This course was a *single step* that will take me to another. In the end, obtaining a master’s degree in Diplomacy and International Affairs (MDIA) will help me achieve my professional life goals.

Understanding the essay’s structure and format is as essential and crucial as studying the ABC at the elementary school. As an international student at EUCLID, I might focus on different study points in my first Response Paper (RP) than those whose mother tongue is English. However, this course can provide every student with unique *steps* that can result in the same beautiful *journey*.

2) THE BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

The first chapter of the ACA-401 Period 1 Coursepack explains the basics of essay writing that gives an easy-to-understand explanation of organizing a set of ideas into a

standard written text. I often make public speeches and presentations in my work. While I studied the chapter, I discovered several similarities between presentations and academic papers in terms of structure and the process of creating them. For example, both of their forms consist of introduction, body, conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3) parts. The method of information gathering, drawing up an initial plan, researching a topic, editing, and providing a reference to specific information (EUCLID 2019, 1–2, 4) also represent those similarities. I found out that the presentation skills I accumulated during my professional career can help me understand **academic writing** basics at EUCLID. However, in my presentation, I usually target the everyday people by delivering information entertainingly; on the other hand, the academic paper should be “academic” used in universities and scholarly publications. I soon had to realize that I need improvement in **academic writing** skills to be able to, as in our coursepack, it reads about the purpose of academic essay writing, “persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1).

3) PLAGIARISM

The second chapter of the ACA-401 Period 1 Coursepack covers the topic of **plagiarism**. It explains how to avoid **plagiarism** by “citing the author or source that has provided the information” (EUCLID 2019, 6). I had an experience in junior high school when my schoolmate borrowed my textbooks and copied my homework assignment using it her own and later got an A-grade. I was disappointed and felt wrong about it. It is probably how the authors might feel when someone else uses their work without giving the author credit.

Plagiarism, i.e., using someone else’s intellectual property, is an “unaccepted academic practice” (EUCLID 2019, 5). In *Stop Plagiarism: A Guide to Understanding and Prevention*, it mentions that “**plagiarism** is a problem that continues to grow” (Cvetkovic and Anderson 2010, 11). As stated in the third chapter of the ACA-401 Period 1, it is not allowed for EUCLID students to do **plagiarism** when writing (EUCLID 2019, 5–16), which I consider an important message and a rule to follow not only at EUCLID but also in my academic career from now.

Furthermore, **plagiarism** in the coursepack comes in the second chapter (EUCLID 2019, 5–13) after the first chapter (EUCLID 2019, 1–4), where we understood essay writing principles. That said, we shall also consider the importance of this topic. It is also easy to realize the value of **plagiarism** by examining the following publications on this theme. One of them is *The Bluebook*, formally titled *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation* (Review et al. 2010). The entire book, which is 511 pages long, is a citation guide for legal materials. The other book is *The Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999) is a textbook written for high school students. This book contains sections about **plagiarism** (EUCLID 2019, 143, 229), the utility of paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 216), and quotations (EUCLID 2019, 50, 399–401, 405), educate students on the topic from a young age. Referring to Cvetkovic’s and Anderson’s views in the publication mentioned above in the second paragraph, “recent findings concur, showing a [positive] change in student behavior regarding **plagiarism** after educational tutorials” (Cvetkovic and Anderson 2010, 12), which confirms the

importance of education in the prevention of **plagiarism**. I fully agree with this finding, and I was pleased to read about it in the coursepack as well.

4) LITERATURE AND LANGUAGE FOR INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS

As an international student at EUCLID whose English is not her first language, writing a university-level essay takes extra practice, time, and patience. In the following categories, I sorted out three themes I especially acknowledge when I write papers.

a) Literature

Chapter 3 and Chapter 4 of the coursepack align applicable rules of writing and technical literature examples. I examined this part of the learning material very well since my mother tongue is Hungarian, and Japanese is the language I use for daily communication. Studying these chapters, I aimed to understand and improve English writing skills, among other skills, such as staying focused, writing clearly, and supporting assertions (EUCLID 2019, 14–15).

b) American versus British English

In Chapter 6, I could grab a general picture of the differences between **American and British English**. The explanation was handy and helped me in brushing up my previous knowledge on the topic.

I started to study British English at a secondary school in Hungary because it was “standard English,” as my teachers always said. Later I realized that my international friends studying American English did not understand the words “pullover” as a sweater, “rubber” as an eraser, and “zebra crossing” as a crosswalk. Aside from the vocabulary difference (EUCLID 2019, 30), we can also find specific spelling (EUCLID 2019, 28) and grammar differences (EUCLID 2019, 29) between **American and British English**.

EUCLID recommends using American English (EUCLID 2019, 24) for essay writing. Also, American English is currently the dominant influence on “world English” (EUCLID 2019, 27).” These are the two reasons I will inaugurate a new policy of using American English to communicate with my teachers and essay writing.

c) Using active voice

We do not use the **passive voice** in the Hungarian language often, but *it is more frequently used* in Japan than in some other countries. It is because the Japanese culture is indirect, so the Japanese language. It is essential to use the **passive voice** in Japanese to

express feelings naturally and sound like a native speaker or writer. Since I have been living in Japan for 18 years, I often use **passive voice**, which influences my English writing habits.

I have started to use the Grammarly Premium writing assistant application to write texts in the Microsoft Word program as the university recommended in orientation materials (EUCLID 2019, 3). It helps me brushing up the grammar and eliminate writing errors. It also offers specific suggestions to improve my writing, especially choosing active voice instead of **passive voice**, which is one of the rules or writing techniques of the Eleven (11) Important Reminders (EUCLID 2019, 17) in Chapter 4. For example, Grammarly Premium asked to consider correcting the **passive voice** in the ‘it is more frequently used’ expression in the first sentence in the first paragraph (underlined above) to *Japanese use it frequently* instead. (For illustration purposes, I kept the **passive voice** sentence above.) With Grammarly Premium, I feel more confident to write, and I keep learning from my mistakes to write correctly without assistance.

5) **RIGHT KNIFE FOR WRITING**

Brad Samuel Leone is an American chef and popular YouTube personality. He said on Bon Appetit online magazine (<https://www.bonappetit.com/>) that “Buying knives can be an intimidating experience. They come in all different shapes and sizes, all of which do certain jobs—you wouldn’t want to use a slicer to core a tomato (“How to Care for Your Kitchen Knives at Home - Bon Appétit | Bon Appetit” n.d.)” I agree with this statement. We need to select among specific tools or styles to perform appropriately and achieve the expected result in the highest quality. It might apply to academic writing to choose the *right knife* for the best work. Why would I write following the BBC News **style guide** to my teachers at EUCLID if I am requested to follow a different guideline?

Chapter 5 aims to address the impact of **style guides**, i.e., the reference books that provide writing styles and rules to different genres such as “technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting (EUCLID 2019, 24).” For instance, as a **style guide** for writing papers, students at EUCLID must follow EUCLID guidelines and use Templates provided by the university to achieve coherent and consistent writing material (EUCLID 2019, 24). I find it very useful, and I agree to have **style guides** that can establish standard style requirements to improve communication and share identity with the audience.

The **Chicago Manual of Style (CMS)** contains comprehensive style guidelines about text formatting, quotation, and citation (EUCLID 2019, 44) for academic papers. I later learned that it is used mostly in the humanities and social sciences, including history and arts. After a close study, I understood that **CMS** often refers students to the Turabian Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations (EUCLID 2019, 44) **style guide** for its navigation ease and use. I was confused about understanding the dates correctly, so that I was pleased to note the proper form of the dates. It says the universal or European format, Day Month Year (e.g., 1 March 2021), has been superseded, and the standard American format, Month Day, Year (e.g., March 1, 2021) is recommended to use.

6) LATIN EXPRESSIONS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Since my junior-high-school years, I have been using simple **Latin expressions and abbreviations**, such as “etc.” (et cetera), “i.e.” (id est), “AM” (ante meridiem), and “PM” (post meridiem). Latin words come in a small package with a lot of meaning so that it is comfortable to use them. Several studies agree that “etc.”, “i.e.”, and “e.g.” are the most often misused **Latin abbreviations**. The Writing Center of the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill calls the three **Latin abbreviations** “the big three” and explains on their website how these three words are misused (<https://writingcenter.unc.edu/tips-and-tools/latin-terms-and-abbreviations/>). It says that all the listed items before “etc.” should be of the same kind. (“Latin Terms and Abbreviations – The Writing Center • University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill” n.d.) Thus when we see a sentence like “I am interested in music: hard rock, astronomy, cooking, etc.,” then “etc.” is considered incorrect here. Furthermore, the Writing Center outlines that “i.e.” and “e.g.” are the “most frequently confused terms.” As I studied their usage further, I realized that “i.e.” is specific and describes an exclusive set, and the “e.g.” is nonexclusive and indicates one or more elements of a group. “He is a competitor in the Olympic Games, i.e. he is a good sportsman” “is an example of using “i.e.” properly. “He likes to do sports e.g., swimming, running and bicycling” is to introduce examples of something using “e.g.”

7) CONCLUSION

I made the first few inches of my first step at EUCLID by understanding the orientation materials, studying the ACA-401 Period 1 Coursepack, and watch the EUCLID Video on Academic Paper Writing. With the new skills in literature, **American English**, active voice, and **Latin expressions and abbreviations**, etc., I carefully proceed to the next step of my journey. According to the Weekly Writing Update insights report from Grammarly Premium I received on May 2, 2021. by email, my productivity showed a higher rate than 97% of Grammarly Premium users globally, and I used more unique words than 82% of others. It adds further confidence to my future essay writing.

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